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FREEDOM OF THE INFORMATION SPACE. IS IT A REALITY OR ILLUSION?

The purpose: to define and analyze the limits of freedom and personal fulfillment in the information space in accordance with the change of the vector information and technical characteristics of social development. **Methodology** of scientific cognitive activity allows you to explore new educational requirements, acquisition of new skills, knowledge and new ways of thinking that can provide adequate person entering into a different social environment to change the parameter; identify behavioral change person's standards and values. **Scientific novelty** reflected in the correlation of real human freedom posed by the technological capabilities of the time, and the imaginary freedom that can undermine the stability of the information society on a number of basic directions of its development. **Conclusions:** 1) socialization in the new socio-cultural information space involves the formation of a complex system of person's intellectual and emotional development. It demands ability to interact with a lot of information, ability to define a kind of needed information and self-analysis of information and communication space and behavior. 2) There is a lot of freedom in media space nowadays. People faced with the problem of increasing the amount of information. To fit into information flow human should change the way he thinks: develop skills in algorithmic approach to information processing, structured analytical thinking. It requires a structured analytical thinking. 3) The open architecture of the Internet space allows creating new areas and communities. It expands the boundaries of existing online communities. The new communicative surroundings are radically transforming traditional communication between people. It is destroying channel information, experience and spiritual values created by men. Absolute informational availability creates an illusion of complete human's independence from social relations and personal communication, isolates people from each other, deprives of a sense of belonging and creates the position of bystander. 4) So called freedom has created new life strategies and undermines the stability of the information society.

Key words: Real freedom, imaginary freedom, meaning, information, life strategies.

Actuality of the research

The transformation of the system of economic management and social life embodied in a fundamentally new stage of socio-economic progress is called global information society. It is an age of electronic economics, online communities and organizations with no borders. It has changed economics, social dimensions of people's life. Now we can see new ways of communication between technologies, information and men. The new level of interaction between technology, information and men, a huge flow of information that is easy to access has changed the boundaries of people's freedom, expanded opportunities for self-realization options in a new socio-cultural dynamics in the 21st century. In accordance with the vector of information and specifications of the society, the man's place in the information space changes too.

Purpose

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Basic material

Society traditionally implements three types of interconnected social interactions. It's people's integration into social groups that combine into an integrated system. It's the society's differentiation, which means specification of its groups, communities, social organizations and institutions. It is different groups and communities' separation according to their interests. The main feature of the modern society is to find meanings in a big amount of information.

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Niklas Luhmann made an analysis of the modern society. He defined it like communication system. The society uses new ways to communicate turning into a general network of virtual reality. At the same time, we can see how virtual reality turns into true reality (1)

Scientists who explore priorities of modern social dynamics (J. Niklas, Manuel Castells, Niklas Luhmann) believe that media space expands unpredictably. The evolution of the social use of information technology increases the level of users' freedom and meets their interests.

"The possibilities of operating information in such a system are virtually unlimited, except opportunities disposal own freedom of the users. The same series includes such features as new conditions of accumulation and evaluation of information; the possibility to separate the processes of the message and perception; erasing almost all spatial, status and property within the limits of communication, etc." [2]

People's freedom involves their activities and attitude to the World. It's actually determined by human's actions and their self-consciousness. Freedom is an opportunity of making a choice. Freedom means an action defined by well-needed demand in condition of a choice from different opportunities. For the implementation of a free choice, there should be no external compulsion and prohibition. Consciousness and reflection give us ability to see options and help us to choose priorities. Because the choice we have is free. Your choice can be free only when you have your own values, goals and ideals. People should understand why they need freedom and how they could use it for their own or other people's sake. Freedom is an opportunity to act according to your own guidelines, dreams, goals. The peculiarity of media space is that it creates some problems. We have an information overdose. That's why we cannot manage information flows, make right choices and figure out what we actually need at this time to solve a particular problem. You need to change the way you think to handle the influence of information flow. You should evolve skills in algorithmic approach to information processing, and structured analytical thinking.

It is important to know that socialization in the new information space presupposes forming of intellectual and emotional development of human which is based on abilities for imaginative think-

ing, conversation and creativity, ability to interact with a large volume of information flows and formulate information needs. It is important to purposefully use the information and analyze your communication space and behavior. It is always a process of mutual adaptation between the individual and the social world. It means socialization. It's an objective and subjective occurrence in specific social relations. As for the society, it means the institutionalization of relationships. Creating a system of rules, regulations and principles with which the individual will coordinate their individual behavior.

"Human submerged into cultural space of symbolic and historical processes. Socialization is the process of self-identification in the symbolic reality. This process means entry into the field of human culture including mastering, revealing its meanings and transformation into characteristic of his personality". (3)

Growth of information technologies requires new approach to education such as gaining new skills, knowledge and new ways of thinking. It provides appropriate entrance into the new social environment where parameters of human's existence changed.

New telecommunication technologies are totally changing the way people interact with each other. The open architecture of the Internet space allows creating new areas and communities. Laptops, smartphones, new medical technologies provide exceptional flexibility and freedom. They promote occurrence of dynamic models of joint activity that has a positive impact on the entire system of economic management. Mobile technologies' development and the emergence of wireless technology lines connected to the Internet have opened up new opportunities for access to business information, Internet services and communication with partners. It helps to make key decisions, regardless of users' location. The combination of advanced wireless technologies has changed the potential of social networks. Video and instant messaging via the Internet expands the boundaries of existing online communities making them more dynamic, interactive, popular and reputable. Increasing the number of interactions leads to their intensification and expansion of social areas involved in online stream contacts. For example, on Runet almost 150 thousand new names appeared during the previous 6 months. Runet has existed

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for almost 20 years. It has united about 5 million users during this period. The person who is not an Internet user is less competitive.

At the same time, new technologies increase the number of online communities that exist on the Web as real social and cultural context has a powerful influence on the shaping of its participants. Currently there is real social and cultural context, which has powerful leverage to its participants. New features of online communities allow its members to establish new rules of social and economic behavior and governing their institutional arrangements. The new communicative surroundings are radically transforming traditional communication between people. It is destroying channel information, experience and spiritual values created by men. Virtual reality is changing consciousness, psychology of perception of the world, is actively displacing traditional culture, the culture of reading books, classical art, and traditional forms of communication, and radically distorting the internal world of personality.

The information and communication space is changing behavioral standards and value orientations. Free autonomy, which people have nowadays, allows them to change their corporate communications, immersed in the social community, to learn and to follow different cultural traditions. Absolute informational availability creates an illusion of complete human's independence from social relations and personal communication, isolates people from each other, deprives of a sense of belonging and creates the position of bystander. Semblance of freedom distorts the integrity of the individual being.

So-called freedom has created new life strategies the impact of the perceived human need to belong to a certain social community, the state, etc., replacing it with intention to escape from the harsh social relations that determine their behavior. Socially significant forms of self-realization ceased to be an internal need and a person's reference point is in his activities, in his living space. He tries to get rid of the obvious belonging to a social group that sets global standards of economic, cultural and emotional behavior. A person thinks that its freedom becomes restricted. Personality totally loses its identity and does not notice how it loses its personal relevance. André Santini made an analysis of the modern "digital person". He insists that collaboration with the government rather than

opposition guarantees individual freedom, pluralism of opinions and different ways of life in the digital surroundings [4].

The imaginary freedom undermines the stability of the information society in several areas:

- unmanaged and poorly controlled amount of information gives a lot of ways of manipulating inhabitant's consciousness and people's opinion;
- a small marginal group begins to provide leverage on people who contact with them;
- so-called free active communication detrimental effect on the social connexion. Loneliness, depression, disturbance of the adequacy of perception of the society, bad communicative skills, and the need for emotional direct contact with another person are the side effects of this.
- undertaken by control by the public services is perceived as incompatible with personal freedom and generates ambiguous interpretation by the various members of society;
- inner people's freedom deforms, the rejection of the traditional system of moral principles leads to imaginary freedom of choice without any guidelines on human values, there is moral degradation. This is a serious threat to the society.

These negative trends have emerged because of an economically viable, but at the same time, unstoppable development of information technologies without saving the moral, ethical, universal norms and principles of communication, developed over thousands of years of human history for self-reproduction and further development of the productive society. Dynamics of technological breakthrough in the social development of the XXI century, based on information technologies, provides a tremendous opportunity for individual self-realization in a free information and communication space. However, this has led to a paradoxical effect, which is to try to implement not the best abilities but basic human needs.

The development of the modern society exposes exclusion and destruction of the main determinants of the development of a person that is embedded in the activities of the nature of personality's aspiration for self-determination. Therefore, since the man is standing in front of the acute problem of preserving his integrity, awareness of the uniqueness and diversity of every personality. The solution to this problem lies in the formation of friendly technological advances of the social surroundings, in search of new productive approaches

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to the understanding of contemporary personality, to identify the social significance of transforming orientation and new aesthetic creativity, is the basis of self-determination of the person in any era.

Scientific novelty

Scientific novelty reflected in the correlation of real human freedom posed by the technological capabilities of the time, and the imaginary freedom that can undermine the stability of the information society on a number of basic directions of its development.

Conclusions

1) socialization in the new socio-cultural information space involves the formation of a complex system of person's intellectual and emotional development, which combines such aspects as:

- universal potential for imaginative thinking;
- communication and creativity;
- ability to interact with a lot of information;
- ability to define a kind of needed information;
- use the information purposefully;
- self-analysis of information and communication space and behavior.

2) freedom defined by human activity and his personality. Essence of freedom is an opportunity to make a choice. People faced with the problem of

increasing the amount of information. It becomes difficult to navigate in the content and manage it. In addition, it is difficult to protect itself from its superabundance and be able to choose exactly what we need to solve the problem in this moment. To fit into information flow human should change the way he thinks: develop skills in algorithmic approach to information processing, structured analytical thinking.

3) The open architecture of the Internet space allows creating new areas and communities. It expands the boundaries of existing online communities. New features of online communities allow its members to establish new rules of social and economic behavior and governing their institutional arrangements. The new communicative surroundings are radically transforming traditional communication between people. It is destroying channel information, experience and spiritual values created by men. Absolute informational availability creates an illusion of complete human's independence from social relations and personal communication, isolates people from each other, deprives of a sense of belonging and creates the position of bystander.

4) So called freedom has created new life strategies and undermines the stability of the information society.

LIST OF REFERENCE LINKS

1. Niklas Luhmann. Einführung in die Systemtheorie. (Hrsg. Dirk Baecker)/ Carl-Auer-Systeme Verlag, Heidelberg 2002
2. E.A. Lavrenchuk. Autopoyezis. Vox an electronic journal of philosophy. <http://vox-journal.org>
3. Elena Korableva. Paradigm for contemporary symbolic reality / Anthropological Measurements of Philosophical Research. No 4 (2013) P. 91-99
4. E. Gorny. Digital human and his rights. URL: http://www.zhurnal.ru/staff/gorny/texts/chart_hd.html.

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СВОБОДА ІНФОРМАЦІЙНОГО ПРОСТОРУ: РЕАЛЬНІСТЬ ЧИ ІЛЮЗІЯ?

Мета роботи: визначити та проаналізувати межі можливостей і свободи самореалізації людини в інформаційному просторі відповідно до зміни вектора інформаційно-технічних характеристик соціального розвитку. **Філософська методологія** науково-пізнавальної діяльності дозволяє досліджувати нові вимоги до освіти, придбання нових навичок, знань і нового мислення, які здатні забезпечити людині адекватне входження в інше соціальне середовище зі зміненими параметрами буття; позначити зміну поведінкових стандартів і ціннісних орієнтацій особистості. **Наукова новизна** відображена у співвіднесенні реальної свободи людини,

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яка породжується технологічними можливостями часу, і уявною свободою, яка здатна розхитати стійкість інформаційного суспільства по ряду базових напрямків його розвитку. **Висновки:** 1) соціалізація в інфокомунікаційному просторі формує складну систему інтелектуального та емоційного розвитку особистості, вимагає активних навичок взаємодії із збільшеними інформаційними потоками, розуміння своїх інформаційних потреб та інформаційно-комунікативної поведінки; 2) свобода медіапростору, в умовах збільшення обсягу інформації, вимагає структурованого аналітичного мислення, розвитку навичок алгоритмічного підходу до обробки інформації; 3) відкрита архітектура інтернет-простору створює нові соціальні середовища, розширює межі існуючих онлайн-спільнот, кардинально перетворює традиційні види міжособистісного спілкування, руйнуючи канал передачі «з рук у руки» накопиченого досвіду і духовних цінностей, змінює поведінкові стандарти і ціннісні орієнтації особистості, породжує ілюзію повної незалежності людини від соціальних зв'язків і міжособистісного спілкування, веде до ізоляції людей один від одного, до втрати відчуття причетності часу; 4) уявна свобода породила нові життєві стратегії, розхитуючи стійкість інформаційного суспільства.

Ключові слова: свобода реальна, свобода уявна, сенс, інформація, життєві стратегії.

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СВОБОДА ИНФОРМАЦИОННОГО ПРОСТРАНСТВА: РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ ИЛИ ИЛЛЮЗИЯ?

Цель работы: определить и проанализировать границы возможностей и свободы самореализации человека в информационном пространстве в соответствии с изменением вектора информационно-технических характеристик социального развития. **Философская методология** научно-познавательной деятельности позволяет исследовать новые требования к образованию, приобретению новых навыков, знаний и нового мышления, которые способны обеспечить человеку адекватное вхождение в иную социальную среду с изменившимися параметрами бытия; обозначить изменение поведенческих стандартов и ценностных ориентаций личности. **Научная новизна** отражена в соотнесении реальной свободы человека, порождаемой технологическими возможностями времени, и мнимой свободы, способной расшатать устойчивость информационного общества по ряду базовых направлений его развития. **Выводы:** 1) социализация в инфокоммуникационном пространстве формирует сложную систему интеллектуального и эмоционального развития личности, требует активных навыков взаимодействия с возросшими информационными потоками, понимания своих информационных потребностей и информационно-коммуникативного поведения; 2) свобода медиaprостранства, в условиях нарастания объема информации, требует структурированного аналитического мышления, развития навыков алгоритмического подхода к обработке информации; 3) открытая архитектура интернет-пространства создает новые социальные среды, расширяет границы существующих онлайн-сообществ, кардинально преобразует традиционные виды межличностного общения, разрушая канал передачи «из рук в руки» накопленного опыта и духовных ценностей, меняет поведенческие стандарты и ценностные ориентации личности, порождает иллюзию полной независимости человека от социальных связей и межличностного общения, ведет к изолированности людей друг от друга, к потере ощущения сопричастности времени; 4) мнимая свобода породила новые жизненные стратегии, расшатывая устойчивость информационного общества.

Ключевые слова: свобода реальная, свобода мнимая, смысл, информация, жизненные стратегии.

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REFERENCES

1. Niklas Luhmann. Einführung in die Systemtheorie. (Hrsg. Dirk Baecker)/ Carl-Auer-Systeme Verlag. Heidelberg 2002
2. E.A. Lavrenchuk. Autopoiesis. Vox an electronic journal of philosophy. <http://vox-journal.org>
3. Elena Korableva. Paradigm for contemporary symbolic reality / Anthropological Measurements of Philosophical Research. No 4 (2013) P. 91-99
4. E. Gorny. Digital human and his rights. URL: http://www.zhurnal.ru/staff/gorny/texts/chart_hd.html.

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